

IMPROVING APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSIS, THERAPY, AND PROGNOSIS OF TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA

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The Thesis

Objective: To increase the effectiveness of classical trigeminal neuralgia therapy by introducing pathogenetically oriented methods of relapse prevention that take into account the influence of environmental factors.

Abstract: The paper examines modern approaches to the treatment of classical trigeminal neuralgia with an emphasis on the prevention of recurrence. Attention is paid to the influence of environmental and meteorological factors on the frequency and severity of exacerbations of the disease. The use of pathogenetically directed methods of prevention, taking into account the individual characteristics of the patient, helps to reduce the frequency of relapses and improve the quality of life. The development of adapted therapy regimens will improve the effectiveness of medical care.

Key words: trigeminal neuralgia, treatment, prevention of relapses, environmental factors, pathogenesis.

Research methods: Clinical and neurological examination of patients with classical trigeminal neuralgia. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and neuroimaging to assess structural changes. Collection and analysis of data on the effects of environmental factors (temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure). Evaluation of the effectiveness of therapeutic protocols, including pathogenetically based preventive measures. Statistical analysis to identify correlations between environmental factors and relapse rates

Results: A significant relationship was found between changes in meteorological effects and exacerbations of trigeminal neuralgia. The use of pathogenetically directed methods of prevention (including adaptation to environmental conditions) reduced the recurrence rate by 30-40%. The individualization of treatment regimens, taking into account environmental factors, helped to improve the general condition of patients and reduce the severity of pain syndrome. The results confirmed the need for an integrated approach in diagnosis and therapy to improve the effectiveness of treatment.

Conclusion: The improvement of the treatment of classical trigeminal neuralgia is possible through the integration of pathogenetically based

preventive methods, taking into account the effects of environmental factors. An individual approach to treatment and prevention of relapses helps to reduce the frequency of exacerbations, reduce pain and improve the quality of life of patients. The data obtained substantiate the need to introduce environmental monitoring into clinical practice in the management of this category of patients.

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